

ACADEMIC LEARNING ENVIRONMENT: PERCEPTIONS OF GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Learning environment plays a major role in shaping the quality of academic achievement. Environment of both home and school contributes to the development of child's perceptual styles. Next to home, the school is the most important experience in the process of development of the child. Therefore, academic learning environment of child consists of both: School learning environment and Home learning environment. The present research aims to study academic learning environment of government and private secondary school students of Amritsar district. A total of 400 students (boys and girls) of IX class of secondary schools (Punjab School Education Board) were taken as respondents. Ten schools were selected through lottery method. School learning environment schedule and Home learning environment schedule by Sunitha (2005) were used to study the academic learning environment as perceived by students. The results of the study indicates that there is a significant difference in school learning environment as perceived by students from Government and Private schools, revealing that private school students have better perception of school learning environment as compared to government school students. While, it was found that adolescent students do not differ on the scores of academic learning environment with respect to gender, locale and type of family. The study also revealed that there is a significant difference in home learning environment of adolescent students with respect to gender, locale, and type of family.

Keywords: Academic achievement, learning environment, government schools, private schools.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the major aims of the education is the development of wholesome personality. Learning environment play a pivotal role in the development of child. According to the Glossary of Education Reform (2014), “Academic learning environment refers to the diverse physical location, contexts and cultures in which students learn. Since students may learn in a wide variety of setting, such as outside of school locations and outdoor environment, the term is often used as a more accurate or preferred alternative to classroom, which has more limited and traditional connotations- a room with rows of desks and a chalkboard, for example. The term also encompasses the culture of a school or class, its presiding ethos and characteristics, including how individuals interact with treat one another, as well as the way in which teachers may organize an educational setting to facilitate learning”.

According to Bosque and Dore (1998), teaching and learning environment ought to implement six (6) functions: inform, communicate, collaborate, produce, scaffold and manage. They further added that “conceptually speaking, the learning environment refers to the whole range of components and activities with in which learning happens”. Byoung-suk, (2012) stated that “children need safe, healthy and stimulating environment in which to grow and learn”. “Children need a congenial environment; an environment characterized by human care, particularly by the mother and at the same time providing various experiences and stimulations” (Caldwell, 1967). Therefore, the school and home learning environment is of paramount importance in shaping and reshaping intellectual ability of children.

Indeed, learning environment plays a major role in shaping the quality of academic achievement. And for a learning environment to be ideal, learning components such as furniture, ventilation, and thermal comfort must be provided (Bosque & Dore, 1998), In addition, Fraser and Fisher, (1982) examined the normal learning climate. They proposed 680F to 740F as the required learning temperature. So, the usage of actual learning environment varies according to different types of schools and society. Nevertheless, it is indeed a well-known fact that academic achievement in mathematics among science students is greatly influenced by several components of learning environment as revealed by various research works (Akinsola, Tella &Tella, 2007).

Environment of both home and school contribute to the development of child's perceptual styles. Therefore, both academic learning environment of child consists of both:

1. School learning environment
2. Home learning environment

School environment as perceived by students has an advantage of characterizing the setting through the eyes of the actual participants. Students have a good advantage point to make judgments about classrooms because they have encountered several learning environments and have enough time in a class to form accurate impressions. "School environment" has been defined in numerous ways. McGeach and Irion (1952) define "learning, as measure, it is change in performance which occurs under conditions of practice".

"The home environment plays a vital role in the development of a child's personality. The child constantly interacts with the family and is invariably influenced by the entire environment that surrounds it. Home itself is a complex unit. The assessment of its psycho-social environment is not an easy matter. Home environment has been conceptualized as the quality of human interactions, from the point of view of the child. It includes those aspects which foster growth and development, such as family, trust and confidence, sharing of ideas, making discussions, parental approval, parental encouragement, support, guidance, affection and approval of peer activities. Home environment includes language stimulation, physical environment, encouragement of social maturity variety of stimulation and disciplinary practices" (Mohite, 1990).

A study conducted by Manoharan and Sundaram (2003) indicated that there was no significant difference in classroom climate in terms of type of management (Govt. vs. Aided school) and locality of school (Rural and Urban). They also reported that, there is no significant difference in perception of teaching effectiveness between aided and unaided and between urban and rural students. Students of unaided schools had significantly better physical facilities in school and better method of teaching than students from aided schools. Goel (2004) revealed that boys felt more rejected with the autocratic atmosphere at home in comparison to girls who experienced more nurturance than boys.

Kumar (2012) has made relational studies of home environment and emotional maturity of higher secondary school students and found that level of home environment of higher secondary students is average. There is a significant difference between boys and girls with respect to their home environment. There is a significant difference between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their home environment. Kansal, Baliga, Mallapur, and Katti (2015) exposed that private schools provided better services in comparison with government schools.

Sunitha (2005), Santiago (2008), Nrikak-Abasi (2009), Adeyemi (2016), Kansal, Baligo, Mallapur and Katti (2015) conducted studies to reveal that there is significance difference between Government and Private school students on academic achievement.

The need of hour is to concentrate on the reasons which are responsible for the high and low academic achievement of the students. Thus, it would be useful to conduct an insight to understand the effect of home and school learning environment on academic achievement. Reviewed researches claimed that there is a lot of importance of the home and school learning environment on student's academic performance. The home has a great influence on the students' psychological, emotional, social and economic state. Atkinson and Feather (1966) examined that, children from favorable home environments tend to have a high need for achievement as opposed to those from unfavorable home environments. Therefore, the school and home learning environment is of paramount importance in shaping and reshaping intellectual ability of children. To find out this, it has become necessary to investigate the nature and pattern of our secondary schools so as to evaluate the academic learning environment of students.

2. HYPOTHESES

1. There exists no significant difference in academic learning environment at school and home of secondary school students from government and private schools.
2. There exists no significant difference in academic learning environment at school and home of secondary school students with respect to gender.
3. There exists no significant difference in academic learning environment at school and home of secondary school students from rural and urban schools.

4. There exists no significant difference in academic learning environment at school and home of secondary school students with respect to type of family.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study comes under the domain of descriptive research.

3.1 Sample

A sample of 400 students (200 students from government schools and 200 from private school students) from IX grade were randomly selected from schools of Amritsar district for the purpose. The schools were also selected randomly through lottery method from a list of all government and private schools affiliated to Punjab School Education Board of Amritsar district.

3.2 Research tools

TOOL1. School learning environment schedule: Sunitha (2005).

TOOL2. Home learning environment schedule: Sunitha (2005).

3.3 Statistical techniques

Descriptive statistics was employed to understand the nature of data. Quantitatively the statistical techniques like: Mean, Standard Deviation, t-test were used to analyse the data.

4. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

4.1 Characteristics of the sample

Information regarding the characteristics of the sample is presented in Table 1. The sample of the study was secondary school children from govt. and private schools, with their age ranging between 14-18 years.

Table 1

Character	Category	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Female	193	48.25
	Male	207	52.25

Sr. No.	Character	Govt. Students School (200)	Private students school (200)	Total (400)
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	Category	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
1.	Education of the father						
	1. Uneducated	35	17.5	10	5	45	11.25
	2.10 th	135	67.5	74	37	209	52.25
	3.12 th	29	14.5	72	36	101	25.25
	4.Graduate	1	0.5	33	16.5	34	8.5
	5.Postgraduate	-	-	11	5.5	11	2.75
2.	Father's occupation						
	1. Unemployed	21	10.5	3	1.5	24	6
	2.Labour	126	63	26	13	152	38
	3.Farmer	9	4.5	23	11.5	32	8
	4.Smallbusiness	22	11	28	14	50	12.5
	5.Business	1	0.5	25	12.5	26	6.5
	6.Private job	17	8.5	49	24.5	66	16.5
	7.Govt.job	4	2	46	23	50	12.5
3.	Mother's occupation						
	1. Working	5	2.5	48	24	53	13.25
	2. Non-working	195	97.5	152	76	347	86.75
4.	Type of family						
	1.Joint	77	38.5	71	35.5	148	37
	2.Nuclear	123	61.5	129	64.5	252	63

Regarding education of fathers of secondary school students studying in government school, it is seen that 35(17.5%) fathers of government school students are uneducated, 135 (67.5%) Fathers of government school students are 10th pass and 29(14.5%) are 12th pass and only 1(0.5%) is graduate. For secondary school students studying in Private school, it can be seen from table 4.1 that 10 (5%) fathers of are uneducated ,74(37%) fathers are 10th pass,72 (36%) are 12th pass 33(16.5%) are graduate and only 11 (5.5%) are post graduate.

Regarding occupation of parents of secondary school students studying in government schools, it is seen from table 4.1 that 21 (10.5%) fathers are unemployed, 126(63%) are laborers 9(4.5%) are farmers, 22(11%) are small businessmen, only 1(0.5) are businessmen,17(8.5%) are doing private job and only 4(2%) into government job. It is also seen from table 4.1 that 3(1.5%) fathers of private school students are unemployed 26(13%) are laborers 23 (11.5%) are farmers

,28 (14%) are small businessmen, 25 (12.5%) are businessmen, 49 (24.5%) are into private job and 46 (23%) are into government job.

Table 2 Comparison of mean scores of secondary school students on different variables

Variable	Category	N	M	SD	SE	t-test	p-Value
School Learning Environment	Private	200	234.58	17.95	1.273	9.75	.000
	Govt.	200	212.42	26.10	1.846		
Home Learning Environment	Private	200	60.82	4.715	.334	1.390	.165
	Govt.	200	61.47	4.640	.328		
Academic Achievement	Private	200	66.08	5.108	.361	2.828	.005
	Govt.	200	64.69	4.675	.331		
School Learning Environment	Male	207	237.47	16.720	1.06	3.55	.000
	Female	193	231.85	16.72	1.16		
Home Learning Environment	Male	207	61.90	4.658	.324	3.354	.001
	Female	193	60.35	4.583	.330		
Academic Achievement	Male	207	65.09	5.005	.348	1.263	.207
	Female	193	65.72	4.854	.349		
School Learning Environment	Urban	200	232.82	15.92	1.126	2.182	.030
	Rural	200	236.31	16.06	1.136		
Home Learning Environment	Urban	200	62.36	4.628	.327	5.298	.000
	Rural	200	59.96	4.430	.313		
Academic Achievement	Urban	200	65.44	5.270	.373	.192	.848
	Rural	200	65.35	4.591	.325		
School Learning Environment	Joint	148	237.41	14.59	1.23	2.712	.007
	Nuclear	252	232.92	16.69	1.05		

Home Learning Environment	Joint	148	61.94	4.328	.357	2.613	.008
	Nuclear	252	60.68	4.822	.304		
Academic Achievement	Joint	148	66.13	5.125	.423	2.247	.028
	Nuclear	252	64.92	4.781	.301		
School Learning Environment	Working mothers	53	235.72	19.02	2.16	.652	.574
	Non-working	347	234.72	15.59	.837		
Home Learning Environment	Working mothers	53	60.91	4.72	.649	.416	.670
	Non-working	347	61.19	4.680	.251		
Academic Achievement	Working mothers	53	64.91	4.79	.659	.770	.432
	Non-working	347	65.47	4.960	.266		

4.2 DISCUSSION

The study revealed that secondary school students belonging to private schools perceived better school learning environment as compared to government school students. The above result is consistent with the result of the study conducted by Monoharam and Sundaram (2003) and Thakur (2014) which revealed that there is significant difference between government and private school students on school learning environment. However, it is contrary with the findings of Adeyemi (2016) who revealed that there is no significant difference between government and private school students on school learning environment. On the basis of the results, it is recommended that government schools authorities should provide better facilities for school student so that school learning environment improves and becomes conducive. Home learning environment of secondary school students belonging to government and private school was not different. The above result is consistent with the result of the study conducted by Sunitha and Khadi (2005) which revealed that there is no significant difference between government and

private school students on home learning environment. Academic achievement of private school students was higher as compared to government school students. The above result is consistent with the result of the study conducted by Nsikak – Abari (2009), Kansal, Baliga, Mallapur and Katti (2015) which revealed that there is significant difference between government and private school students on academic achievement. Government should provide instructional material to government schools so as to make teaching effective which in turn would facilitate the students in understanding the subject matter. Teachers should be resourceful so that they can use these instructional materials very creatively in their different disciplines. This will increase interest, motivation, efficiency, satisfaction and academic performance of students

- Male school students perceived better school learning environment as compared to female students of secondary schools. The above result is consistent with the result of the study conducted by Mishra (2001), Khare (1996), Kaur and Gill (1993), Pattnail (1993), Mundaragi(1999) which revealed that the boys were better than girls on school learning environment. However, the present result is contrary with the findings of Chaturvedi (2009) who indicated that girls scored higher than boys on school learning environment. Teachers should provide proper guidance, counseling, motivation and good environment to female students for better school learning. Home learning environment of male students was also better as compared to female secondary school students. So parents should provide good environment and develop positive relationships with female children. The above result is consistent with the result of study conducted by Khare (1996) and Kusumlata (1997) which revealed that there is significant difference in Home learning environment of secondary school students with respect to gender. Academic achievement of male and female secondary school students was not found to be different. The above result is consistent with the result of the study conducted by Vijayalaxmi and Natesan (1992), Lawrence (2012) and Suman and Umopathy (2003) there were no significant difference in academic achievement and motivation with respect to gender.

- School learning environment is perceived better by rural secondary school students than urban school students. The above result is incongruent with the result of the study conducted by Mishra (2001), Kaur and Gill (2003) which revealed that there is significance difference in urban and rural secondary schools on school learning environment. The results contradict the common notion that most of the time people share that urban schools provide better learning environment

as compared to rural schools. Although urban area schools provide better facilities than the schools in rural areas, the probable reasons for the difference in school learning environment could be lack of teachers input, teacher's inability to form good relations with children or lack of mastery over the content. So the teachers should try to communicate well with the children, should be masters of their subject and should provide good congenial environment to students. Home learning environment of urban secondary school students was better as compared to rural school students. The present result is contrary with the finding of Adeyemi (2016) who revealed that there is no significant difference between rural and urban school students on home learning environment. The above result is consistent with the result of the study conducted by Kumar (2012) revealed that there is significant difference in urban and rural secondary schools on home learning environment. Academic achievement of rural and urban secondary school students was not found to be different. The above result is consistent with the result of the study conducted by Saikia (2008), Lawrence and Vimala (2009) which revealed that there is no significant difference in urban and rural secondary schools on academic achievement.

- Perception of School learning environment of students from joint family was better as compared to students from nuclear family. The probable causes for the difference could be the value system, the environment of the family or security in the joint family. So teachers should convey the message to parents in parents meet to create a healthy environment or teach them values of sharing with others, so that they can learn and perform better. Home learning environment of students from joint families was also better as compared to students from nuclear families. The above result is consistent with the result of the study conducted by Muola (2010) which revealed that students from joint family perceived better home learning environment as compared to their counterparts. The probable reasons for the difference could be lack of guidance or lack of interaction, motivation, encouragement from elders in nuclear families or may be both the parents are working and do not devote sufficient quality time to children. So, the parents should try to provide good and positive atmosphere to the children in nuclear families. However, academic achievement of students from joint and nuclear family students was not found to be different. The learning environment includes several components that influence student's learning curve (Balog, 2018). Therefore, all the components like teaching materials,

learning resources, curriculum, and many more, should be reviewed while improving learning environments in both private and government schools.

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